

Multi-fidelity Shape Optimization of Combustion Devices

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Abstract

Due to the distinct combustion properties of hydrogen compared to conventional fossil fuels, novel burner designs are required. Additive manufacturing techniques enable the realization of complex geometries, which can be obtained through simulation-based design optimization. However, the considerable costs associated with high-fidelity CFD simulations of the governing physical processes in hydrogen burners limits their direct use in optimization. Multi-fidelity surrogate modeling provides an efficient alternative by combining inexpensive low-fidelity with accurate high-fidelity simulation results. We present a modular toolchain for simulation-based shape optimization of combustion devices that integrates (low-fidelity) RANS and (high-fidelity) LESs, which provide the basis for a multi-fidelity surrogate model. Inherently, this approach incorporates time-averaged and transient characteristics of the newly designed burners. Our approach is therefore capable of capturing both, quantities derived from averaged solutions and those influenced by transient dynamics. We apply the multi-fidelity toolchain to the optimization of the internal geometry of a weakly turbulent hydrogen burner nozzle. The results show that purely geometric modifications can significantly influence mixture characteristics through changes in flow features such as recirculation zones and jet-in-crossflow interactions. The optimization toolchain reliably produces designs that meet the desired mixture characteristics in both time-averaged and transient metrics. The results demonstrate the efficacy of this toolchain for the design optimization of burner nozzles (or other combustion devices) and it is suited to make use of the design freedom offered by additive manufacturing.

Keywords: Multi-fidelity Optimization, Shape optimization, Fluid Mixing Optimization, Hydrogen, Inverse design, Burner design

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Article highlights

- Development of a flexible and efficient multi-fidelity design optimization toolchain.
- Application of the toolchain to optimize the internal nozzle geometry of a hydrogen burner.
- Assessment of the benefits of multi-fidelity optimization with scale-resolving simulations over single-fidelity optimization.

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1. Introduction

Innovative burner designs suited for hydrogen combustion are required to account for the unique combustion characteristics of hydrogen compared to conventional fossil fuels [1–3]. These include the high flame temperature of hydrogen-air flames leading to NO_x formation [4], and high thermal stress induced in the burner material, as well as its high flame speed and its high propensity to flame flashback into the burner nozzle [1, 2, 5]. To address the challenges of safe hydrogen combustion with low NO_x emissions, the internal geometry of a hydrogen burner nozzle is optimized with a multi-fidelity shape optimization toolchain based on Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) computations and Large Eddy Simulations (LES). As will be shown in this work, a combination of RANS and LES provides an advantageous balance between accurate prediction of the mean flow and transient fluctuations at moderate computational cost.

With the increasingly available computational power, the inclusion of both high- and low-fidelity simulation techniques becomes feasible for many industry-relevant applications [6]. When combined with Additive Manufacturing (AM), which alleviates conventional manufacturing constraints, a pairing of computer-aided design optimization and AM enables the creation of innovative and unprecedented product designs [7]. While design optimization based on CFD simulations has been applied to many aerodynamic and heat transfer problems (e.g. in [8–12]), extending these approaches to simulations involving multiple interacting physical processes remains challenging. For the design of combustion devices, progress is still limited by the computational costs associated with the accurate simulation of chemically reacting flows, including heat transfer, chemical kinetics, and mixing phenomena, among others. Recently, there have been efforts to develop frameworks for gradient-based optimization of combustion devices by solving adjoint equations for reactive flows [13–15]. However, these adjoint frameworks are specific to the application as the adjoint equations depend on the chosen objective metric and the choice of the mixture model, chemistry, and turbulence closure [16]. To reduce the complexity of the system, these frameworks are often

applied to one- or two-dimensional laminar configurations [13, 15]. Gradient-free and surrogate-based optimization frameworks offer an alternative to adjoint frameworks. Such frameworks have been successfully coupled to numerical simulations of chemically reactive flows [17–20], as well as to experiments [21, 22] to develop optimal designs. This approach is now further extended to multi-fidelity optimization: By combining data from high-fidelity (HF) LES and computationally less intensive, low-fidelity RANS computations in a multi-fidelity (MF) surrogate model, the optimization process becomes more efficient and more accurate than single-fidelity optimization. The hierarchical Kriging surrogate model by Han and Görtz [23] is used as a MF surrogate. Other MF surrogate modeling approaches have been explored in the literature. For example, Usandivaras et al. [24] optimized a rocket engine using neural networks and transfer learning to combine both fidelity levels.

We utilize the aforementioned optimization toolchain to mitigate the greater flashback propensity of premixed hydrogen flames compared to hydrocarbon flames [25–30]. A second optimization target is to reduce NO_x formation, which originates from the high combustion temperature of hydrogen [4]. With a similar goal (reduced flashback propensity and NO_x emissions), Schmidt et al. [31] designed a burner nozzle, which is shown in Fig. 1. For operational safety, hydrogen and air are being supplied separately into the burner. Inside the burner nozzle a spatially inhomogeneous, partially premixed hydrogen-air mixture develops. The local mixture distribution at the nozzle outlet and the flame that is established with this reference design is presented in the center. For comparison, a perfectly premixed flame with otherwise identical operating conditions is presented to the right. The methodology of the flame simulations follows that of prior work [32].

Schmidt et al. [31] could show that introducing a disk-shaped flowbody in the premixing section significantly improves the mixture formation, consequently decreasing the NO_x emissions of the burner. The impact of the internal geometry on the emissions motivate further geometric optimization of this design

Figure 1: Section cut of the reference design by Schmidt et al. [31] on the left. The local mixture field at the nozzle outlet is indicated with the local equivalence ratio. The flame that is established on the burner nozzle is shown in the center. For comparison, a premixed flame is presented on the right.

concept. Due to the weakly turbulent operating conditions in the investigated nozzles and the separately-supplied fuel and oxidizer, mixture variations at the outlet of the burner nozzle are expected. The impact of mixture variations on the stabilization of hydrocarbon flames has been investigated (e.g., [33–37]), and it could be shown that targeted mixture variations can improve the stability of the flame [34]. This concept of stabilizing hydrocarbon flames through mixture variations has been transferred to hydrogen flames by Vance and Scholtissek [38] to reduce their propensity to flame flashback. Flashback of burner-stabilized flames typically initiates at the nozzle wall in the boundary layer where the flow velocity is low due to the no-slip condition [39–41]. While the flow velocity is reduced, the local flame speed remains unchanged, or may even increase in the presence of hot nozzle walls, as Soret diffusion of hydrogen alters the local hydrogen–air mixture and thereby affects the flame speed [5, 42]. To counteract this effect, Vance and Scholtissek [38] introduced targeted mixture variations with fuel-lean mixtures in vicinity to the nozzle

wall, thereby decreasing the local flame speed. This targeted mixture field at the nozzle outlet is presented in Fig. 2. Fuel-lean mixtures are visible toward the nozzle wall, while the core flow carries a higher fuel fraction. In the following, we will refer to this radial mixture distribution as “mixture stratification”.

Figure 2: Targeted mixture distribution at the nozzle outlet with a fuel-lean mixture near the nozzle wall and a higher fuel fraction in the core flow as envisioned in [38].

Vance and Scholtissek [38] observed a decrease in flashback propensity while maintaining similar power outputs compared to perfectly premixed conditions [38]. This raises the question which internal geometries produce radially stratified mixtures with leaner compositions near the nozzle wall. This inverse design problem is addressed in this work using a simulation-based shape optimization approach and the radial mixture stratification at the nozzle outlet is chosen as a second optimization objective. Additionally, utilizing data from HF LES, transient characteristics are included in the optimization by penalizing large temporal fluctuations in the near-wall mixture, that may trigger flame flashback.

The objectives of this study are

- I: Development of a modular and efficient toolchain for simulation-based MF shape optimization of mixture-controlling internal nozzle structures.
- II: Exploration of the potential of MF (RANS & LES) design optimization of combustion devices

and comparison to single-fidelity (RANS only) optimization.

III: Demonstration of the capability of the toolchain by applying it to an inverse design problem of a hydrogen burner nozzle targeting operational safety and low pollutant emissions, and identifying the globally optimal design, as well as local optima.

The paper is structured as follows: First, the shape optimization toolchain is described in detail (Sec. 2). Then, the toolchain is applied to optimize the internal geometry of a hydrogen burner nozzle (Sec. 3), followed by the analysis of the obtained nozzle designs in Sec. 4, highlighting the impact of multi-fidelity (MF) optimization over single-fidelity (SF) optimization.

2. Multi-fidelity shape optimization toolchain

In this study, we utilize a MF surrogate model to efficiently optimize the shape of hydrogen burner nozzles using CFD simulations. While surrogate-based optimization drastically reduces the number of required simulations, building an accurate surrogate still requires $\sim 10^2$ simulations (see Sec. 3.4). This can be a prohibitive requirement for certain applications. Incorporating data from less accurate but computationally cheaper LF models into the surrogate model is an efficient approach to obtaining a sufficiently accurate MF surrogate model with reduced computational costs [43]. In this study, LF data are provided by RANS computations, while HF data that captures the transient flow behavior of the nozzle designs are obtained through LES. In both the HF and the LF simulations, the compressible Navier-Stokes equations are solved. Additional transport equations for the mass fraction of the major chemical species H_2 , O_2 and N_2 are included. To model diffusive transport, the Hirschfelder and Curtiss approximation [44] with mixture-averaged diffusion coefficients is implemented [45]. During the optimization no chemical reactions are taken into account. Furthermore, the mutual heat transfer between the gas phase (flame, fuel and oxidizer) and solid phase (burner material) as well as the effect that this may have on the mixture formation due to Soret diffusion is neglected.

2.1. Low-fidelity model: RANS

The shear stress transport RANS model by Menter [46] is applied. A simplified 60° wedge-shaped domain is used with periodic boundary conditions on the wedge faces to minimize the computational cost per simulation. The near-wall region is refined to $y^+ \approx 2$. To robustly run the simulations for each of the generated geometries, an in-house steady-state solver is implemented in OpenFOAM [47]. For pressure-velocity coupling the SIMPLE algorithm [48] is used. The library Cantera [49] is coupled to the solver for calculation of the mixture-averaged diffusion coefficients as well as the mixture-dependent fluid transport properties, such as the viscosity and the density. The solver is verified against an time-averaged large eddy simulation (LES). Time-varying under-relaxation factors and second order discretization schemes that fulfill the total variation diminishing (TVD) criterion are employed to ensure fast and robust convergence. An exemplary RANS computation result using the reference geometry [31] is presented in Fig. 3. The qualitative agreement between the RANS predictions and the time-averaged LES results suggests that RANS is capable of approximating the trends of the objective metric with respect to geometric changes, making it a suitable LF model.

2.2. High-fidelity model: LES

In the LES, the full three-dimensional domain is computed and the large, energy-containing turbulent structures are resolved. A fine mesh is employed to capture near-wall turbulence and mixture effects in the nozzle, with the first cell positioned within the viscous sublayer ($y^+ \approx 2$). The σ -model [50] is used for turbulence closure. A transient in-house solver with the PIMPLE algorithm [51] for pressure-velocity coupling is used. Again, Cantera [49] is employed for calculating the mixture-averaged diffusion coefficients. Second-order discretization schemes are applied in both time and space. The capabilities of RANS computations and LESs can be observed in Fig. 3:

2.3. Multi-fidelity surrogate model

Kriging models are a popular choice for SF optimization [43, 52, 53]. Such Kriging models have

Figure 3: Section cut through the reference design [31] as presented in Fig. 1 showing instantaneous and averaged LES results, as well as a RANS computation. For conciseness, only half of the section cut through the LES domain is shown. The flow field is indicated using arrows, while the hydrogen mass fraction, Y_{H_2} , is colored in blue to represent the local gas composition.

been extended to multiple fidelity levels by recursively utilizing Gaussian processes for the approximation of different fidelity levels (e.g., [23, 54, 55]). We utilize the hierarchical Kriging model introduced by Han and Görtz [23] in the present optimization approach. Their model is implemented in python utilizing a LF Kriging approximation from the library scikit-learn [56]. Following Han and Görtz [23], this LF approximation is used as a trend function for the hierarchical Kriging model. To obtain the parameters of the model, the DIRECT algorithm from the library SciPy [57] is used for maximizing the likelihood function as given in [23]. The implementation is verified against the analytical test function of [23, 43], whose results are successfully reproduced in Fig. 4.

2.4. Sampling plan

To accurately represent the user-defined objective function with the surrogate model while minimizing the number of required CFD simulations, an effective sampling strategy is crucial. Usually, an even coverage of the design space is desired to achieve an accurate global approximation [58]. Randomized sam-

Figure 4: Hierarchical Kriging surrogate model by Han and Görtz [23] applied to an analytical test function as described in [23, 43].

pling strategies like Latin hypercube sampling typically achieve good coverage of the design space with few sampling points by varying multiple design variables simultaneously [58]. To further increase the uniformity of the design space coverage of such randomized sampling strategies, fulfilling the orthogonal array property can be enforced [59]. In this work, we use the orthogonal array Latin hypercube sampling plan by Owen [59] for generating both the LF and the HF sampling points. The sampling points are generated a priori and are therefore decoupled from any simulations in progress. This enables the concurrent execution of multiple simulations without requiring inter-process communication between different simulations, allowing effective scalability on large HPC systems.

2.5. Global and local optimization

For achieving the best possible nozzle design, a global optimization approach is required. The single-objective global genetic algorithm that is implemented in Dakota [60] is used in the shape optimization toolchain. Since even the HF simulations may not capture all relevant physical effects, identifying other locally optimal designs for experimental testing or further numerical analysis can be benefi-

cial. This is realized by applying the derivative-free asynchronous parallel pattern search (APPS) algorithm [60–62] to the MF surrogate model. This local algorithm is started from distinct initial points to obtain local optima. The initial points are chosen by identifying promising candidates from the set of LF sampling points that is used for building the surrogate model.

2.6. Automatic optimization toolchain

To efficiently generate and evaluate the sampling points, the toolchain is automated. It is separated into two parts: The optimization framework and the simulation framework. This is illustrated in Fig. 5.

The optimization framework handles design space exploration following the chosen sampling plan (Sec.). In this study, the software Dakota [60] is a key component of the optimization framework by providing the selected sampling strategy and optimization algorithms, as well as a generic interface for coupling external simulations [60]. Since only SF sampling is supported in Dakota [60], the LF and HF sampling points are collected separately. As the chosen surrogate model is implemented in python, the direct python interface of Dakota [60] is used to obtain the set of optimal design variables. The trial points are communicated simultaneously as a “batch” to the python surrogate enabling high-performance evaluation.

The CFD framework handles the execution of the numerical simulations with all required pre- and post-processing steps. These include (1) preparation of the simulation directory, (2) modification of the design according to the parameters specified by the optimization framework, (3) generating the corresponding numerical mesh, (4) executing the simulation, and (5) evaluating the objective function based on the simulation results. To handle these steps, different software tools are combined. To parameterize the geometry and specify suitable design variables, we use a Computer-Aided Design (CAD) tool with standardized export file formats. Thereby, optimized designs can be easily modified and shared for manufacturing. The open-source software FreeCAD [64] is chosen for its python interface which is used for automation of the optimization workflow. Utilizing this interface, a

geometry modification tool is developed that either identifies geometric parameters by their label in the FreeCAD document and modifies them according to the given parameters, or by modifying pre-defined design parameters within FreeCAD. After modification of the geometry, it is exported in the STL format. We found the workflow to be most robust when exporting the geometry in the ISO standard file format STEP [65] first and then triangulating the surfaces using the software gmsh [66] for conversion to STL. A negative of the solid geometry is modeled in FreeCAD that serves as the computational domain for the CFD simulations. The boundary of the domain is split into separate regions to which different boundary conditions are assigned. These regions are retained in the STL file and utilized in the mesh generation process to identify the different boundaries. The geometry modification tool is interfaced with the optimization framework using a YAML file containing information on the FreeCAD document, geometric parameters, and boundary surfaces.

After the modified geometry is exported, the corresponding mesh is generated using the software cfMesh [67]. Although the STL file format is natively supported by cfMesh [67], the geometry representation in the body-fitted mesh is found to be more accurate if the STL file is first converted into the FMS file format. As a last step in the CFD framework, the objective function is evaluated based on the OpenFOAM computation. For maximum flexibility regarding the choice of the objective function, the evaluation of the objective function is realized with a user-defined python script.

To automate execution of all aforementioned software tools, the CFD framework is encapsulated in a shell script. This script is invoked by the optimization framework for each evaluation of the objective function.

3. Application to the inverse design optimization of a hydrogen burner nozzle

To apply this toolchain to the shape optimization of a hydrogen burner nozzle, an initial design idea is parameterized, the operating conditions are set, and an objective function is defined.

Figure 5: Schematic of the simulation-based shape optimization toolchain. Reprinted from [63] under license CC BY 4.0.

3.1. Design parameterization and constraints

The selection of the geometric parameters of the burner nozzle determines the geometries that can be generated during the optimization process and thereby the shape of the optimized design. Inspired by the reference design by Schmidt et al. [31], a prior SF study (RANS only) has been conducted guiding the parameterization for the MF optimization in the present work. It lead to the following findings:

- The hole size in the hydrogen tube has a significant influence on the mixture stratification.
- The shape and size of the flowbody have a significant impact on the turbulent intensity and on the mixture formation inside the burner. Hence, they are key design features for achieving the desired mixture characteristics.
- The outer nozzle geometry has only a minor effect

on the mixture formation. Simultaneously optimizing both the nozzle and the flowbody geometry requires nonlinear constraints to ensure a minimal gap width between flowbody and nozzle. Since they are ignored during sampling, they lead to many failed simulations due to infeasible designs.

These insights inform the design idea and selected parameterization in the present work, which is shown in Fig. 6. The flowbody is parameterized with a spline and the hole size is variable. The spline is modified during the optimization process by moving the handle points indicated with red circles. The smaller blue handle points are fixed in place. The suffix *.x* indicates the axial location of the corresponding handle point, and the suffix *.r* denotes the radial location of the handle point.

Geometric constraints are imposed to ensure the additive manufacturability of the optimized designs.

Figure 6: The parameterization with five design variables used for the optimization.

In particular, the minimum wall thickness is set to 1 mm and a minimum gap width of 1 mm is ensured to prevent blockages of internal channels. To satisfy these requirements, bound constraints, summarized in Tab. 1, and a linear constraint, given in Eqn. 1, are applied to the design variables.

Table 1: Bound constraints to the design variables.

	h.x	p.r	p.x	id.x	fb.x
lower bound (mm)	6.75	5	0	2	1
upper bound (mm)	9.5	8	8	16	23

$$p.x - id.x \leq 1.5 \text{ mm} \quad (1)$$

3.2. Operating conditions

The operating conditions under which the burner are optimized are identical to those used by Schmidt et al. [31] for developing the reference design. They are summarized in Tab. 2 and remain constant during the optimization process. Consequently, the outlet diameter is fixed to prevent a change in bulk velocity at the nozzle outlet. Under the chosen operating conditions, the H_2 and air inlets to the nozzle remain laminar. Weak turbulence is generated due to flow detachment from internal geometric features. At the nozzle outlet, a Reynolds number of $Re \approx 3200$ is reached.

3.3. Objective function

The present optimization aims to solve the inverse design problem of identifying burner geometries that

Table 2: Operating conditions that are used in the present optimization following the Schmidt et al. [31] reference design.

Global equivalence ratio ϕ_g	Bulk velocity u_{bulk}	Thermal power P_{th}
0.67	8.22 m s^{-1}	0.8 kW

yield a radial mixture stratification in the nozzle outlet plane for mitigating the risk of flame flashback, while maintaining a high degree of mixture homogeneity in the angular direction to minimize pollutant emissions. Additionally, we target minimization of temporal fluctuations in the near-wall mixture. The objective function, f , is designed to account for all three desired properties through a weighted sum of the individual properties:

$$\begin{aligned} \min f(\mathbf{x}) &= \Phi_{\text{strat}} + 10 \Phi_{\text{hom}} + 2.5 \Phi_{\text{pen}} \\ \text{s.t. } \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}) &\leq \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where Φ_{strat} , Φ_{hom} , and Φ_{pen} represent metrics for the radial mixture stratification, the homogeneity of the mixture in the angular direction, and a penalty term, respectively. The constraints, $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x})$, are given in Sec. 3.1. The factors that scale each metric are based on prior explorative studies to ensure that each property is in the same order of magnitude. This objective function is used for both HF and LF simulations. The metrics Φ_{strat} and Φ_{hom} are evaluated on the mean mixture field either obtained from the LF RANS computations or from time-averaged HF LES. The HF data is averaged over a timeframe of 0.1 s after the statistically stationary state has been reached and the metrics Φ_{strat} and Φ_{hom} are evaluated on the averaged field. For the reference design, this timeframe corresponds to 385 turbulent integral timescales (integral timescale $\tau \approx 0.26 \text{ ms}$). For completeness, we note that the integral timescale varies across nozzle designs because it depends on internal geometric features (modified during optimization) that induce flow detachment and turbulent structures. The impact of the averaging period on the optimized design is further discussed in Sec. 4.4.

The penalty term, Φ_{pen} , is based on the transient

mixture characteristics obtained from HF simulations and it remains zero for the LF computations. Next, the calculation of each metric is described in detail.

3.3.1. Radial mixture stratification

The degree of mixture stratification, Φ_{strat} , is evaluated by comparing the local mixture at the nozzle outlet against a target mixture profile. Our target profile is based on the work by Vance and Scholtissek [38] and it is shown in Fig. 7. The target profile is characterized by a stratification factor, S , that relates the bulk equivalence ratio, ϕ_b , to the local equivalence ratio, ϕ , weighted by the area of the corresponding annulus in the nozzle outlet plane. In [38], the stratification factor is defined for a step profile with a stratification width, δ , and a wall equivalence ratio, ϕ_w ,

$$S = 1 - \frac{(R - \delta)^2 \phi_b + (2R\delta - \delta^2) \phi_w}{R^2 \phi_b}. \quad (3)$$

This definition is generalized here to account for continuous mixture profiles

$$S = 1 - \frac{\int_0^R \phi(r) r dr}{\int_0^R \phi_b r dr}. \quad (4)$$

The target profile is constructed from a specified global equivalence ratio, ϕ_g , targeted stratification factor, S , and fixed stratification width, δ . The bulk and wall equivalence ratios of the continuous profile, ϕ_b and ϕ_w , are determined in an iterative procedure to maintain the specified global equivalence ratio ϕ_g . The transition width, Δ , (see Fig. 7) is fixed to 0.5 mm and the stratification width, δ , is determined based on the flame thickness and the nozzle radius. The mixture distribution at the outlet plane of the reference design, obtained through a RANS simulation, is presented in Fig. 8. To assess the alignment of this distribution with the desired stratification profile, the field is averaged in the angular direction, as illustrated with the gray circle. Following this approach, an averaged distribution is obtained for different radii (e.g., as shown in Fig. 12 in the right column for different designs). The absolute deviation from the target distribution is calculated for each radius and weighted by the area of the corresponding

annulus. Finally, the average deviation is calculated, resulting in the scalar metric Φ_{strat} that represents the extent to which a specific burner design reproduces the targeted radial mixture stratification.

Figure 7: Construction of the target stratification profile that is to be matched during the optimization.

Figure 8: Distribution of the hydrogen mass fraction at the outlet of the reference design

3.3.2. Angular mixture homogeneity

Figure 8 shows an inhomogeneous mixture with a distinct pattern resulting from the six holes in the central hydrogen tube (see Fig. 1). Since the angular location of the richer-than-average and leaner-than-average regions is prescribed by the location of these holes, the homogeneity of the mixture can be quantified by comparing the stratification factors along radial lines at these angles. This yields a set of stratifi-

cation factors corresponding to the holes and a set of stratification factors corresponding to the blockages. Each set of stratification factors is averaged, and the uniformity of the stratification, Φ_{hom} , is quantified as the difference between each set's mean.

3.3.3. Penalization based on high-fidelity results

The instantaneous mixture fields at the outlet plane contain additional information that can only be obtained from the HF simulations. An exemplary instantaneous mixture field is presented in Fig. 9 (a). Even though the design may look promising based on the averaged field, the transient mixing process can induce fluid elements with richer-than-average mixtures close to the wall. In consequence, these transient phenomena may trigger flame flashback, conflicting with the purpose of the mixture stratification. For calculating the penalty in the HF simulations, the instantaneous clusters of fuel-rich fluid elements must be detected first. Since the mean field is already included in Φ_{strat} and Φ_{hom} , it is subtracted from the instantaneous field for the computation of Φ_{pen} . For the overall lean operating conditions, slightly richer-than-average mixtures result in a higher flame speed. Therefore, only richer-than-average clusters increase the risk of flashback and these regions are colored in Fig. 9 (b). To detect clusters in vicinity of the wall, a critical radius is set for the cluster detection with $r_{\text{crit}} = 2/3 r_{\text{max}}$. SciPy's implementation of the k-means clustering algorithm is utilized to detect the clusters [57]. Since the number of clusters must be prescribed for the algorithm, but is not known a priori, the number of clusters is sequentially increased while monitoring the minimal Euclidean distance between two detected clusters to avoid repeated penalization of the same cluster. The minimal allowed distance between two clusters is set to one third of the outlet's radius. This proves to be a robust approach for automated cluster detection. The detected clusters in the instantaneous mixture field are indicated in Fig. 9 (c). For the penalization, each cluster's location and its mixture are taken into account. A quadratic term for both the radial location and the normalized H₂ mass fraction is chosen to penalize clusters close to the wall with richer-than-average mixtures, yielding one penalty per timestep, $\Phi_{\text{pen},i}$:

Figure 9: (a) Instantaneous field of the H₂ mixture at the outlet of the burner in a LES. (b) Difference between the instantaneous and the averaged field. Only richer-than-average regions are colored. (c) Clusters detected using the k-means clustering algorithm.

$$\Phi_{\text{pen},i} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{clusters}}} 2.5 * \left(\frac{\max(Y_{\text{H2},j})}{Y_{\text{H2},g}} \right)^2 * \left(\frac{r_j - r_{\text{crit}}}{r_{\text{max}} - r_{\text{crit}}} + 1 \right)^2. \quad (5)$$

From this set of penalties (one per timestep), the mean penalty, Φ_{pen} , is computed.

3.4. Required number of sampling points

To determine the optimal number of sampling points, the surrogate model accuracy is systematically evaluated as a function of the sampling size. The number of sampling points is progressively increased, and the resulting model accuracy is assessed using an independent validation dataset comprising 50 randomly selected points. Fig. 10 shows the root mean square prediction error (RMSPE) of the surrogate model constructed on n_{LF} LF sampling points. For this analysis of the sampling size, only LF simulations are utilized and a SF Kriging surrogate model is constructed. Good convergence of the RMSPE can be observed for $n_{\text{LF}} \geq 121$. To allow for failed simulations that cannot be included in the surrogate model, $n_{\text{LF}} = 169$ sampling points are selected for the following optimization.

Figure 10: Root mean square prediction error (RMSPE) of the SF Kriging model for different sampling sizes evaluated against an independent dataset containing 50 trial points.

For the HF simulations, $n_{HF} = 25$ sampling points are selected using the same sampling strategy as for the LF simulations (see Sec.). Due to the extensive resource demand associated with HF LES, a similar analysis of the required number of HF sampling points is not carried out.

4. Optimized designs

Applying the MF shape optimization toolchain yields optimal parameter sets for the chosen parameterization. Next, the mixture formation inside the optimized nozzles is analyzed and the impact of the averaging timeframe on the results is discussed.

4.1. Multi-fidelity optimized burner design

The MF optimized design is presented in Fig. 11 on the left. The holes for hydrogen ejection from the central tube are relatively large, yet remain within the specified bound-constraints. The flowbody has a large radius at the point of initial H_2 injection into the airflow reaching the upper bound for $p.r$ (see Tab. 1). Its tip is curved inward. This is a result of the chosen parameterization: The radial position of the handle point id (see Fig. 6) is not a design variable. However, due to the smoothing behavior of the spline, the radius of the flowbody at this intermediate handle point can be increased by retracting the flowbody’s tip. As this intrusion is challenging to manufacture, and is not based on physical reasons

of the fluid flow, but rather a result of the parameterization, a similar design is manually created while preserving the outer shape of the flowbody. This adjusted design is shown in Fig. 11 on the right.

Figure 11: Left: Section cut of the optimized design obtained using the MF optimization based on RANS and LES computations. Right: For manufacturing adjusted design.

To obtain this optimal design, 169 LF computations and 25 HF computations have been carried out. Out of these simulations 4 HF simulations and 35 LF simulations failed. Out of the failed simulations, 13 % are infeasible since the linear constraints to the design variables are ignored when generating the sampling plan. The MF surrogate model is built on the results of the remaining successful computations.

To highlight the efficacy of the optimization process, the optimized design is compared to the reference design. The mixture distributions at the outlet and the radial mixture profiles are presented in Fig. 12.

Compared to the reference design, the targeted radial mixture stratification is successfully introduced purely through the geometric modifications while a high angular mixture homogeneity is maintained in the MF optimized design. In the temporally averaged mixture field, the adjusted design, “MF.2”, and the MF optimized design, “MF”, are similar featuring a high angular mixture homogeneity and a radial stratification. A slight difference in the degree of radial stratification is apparent as the optimized design features slightly richer mixtures in the center of the nozzle compared to the adjusted design. To indicate how the mixture stratification is realized in this design, a longitudinal slice of the full

Figure 12: Mixtures at the outlet plane of the reference design, “ref.”, the SF optimized design, “SF”, the MF optimum, “MF”, and the for manufacturing adjusted optimum, “MF.2”.

three-dimensional domain of design MF.2 is shown in Fig. 13. Compared to the mixture formation in the reference design (Fig. 3), it is apparent that hydrogen is not ejected as far into the airflow and the flow attaches at the flowbody carrying mixtures with high hydrogen content toward the center.

All objective function values as obtained from RANS computations and LES results, as well as the averaged penalty term, Φ_{pen} , are listed in Tab. 3. A 62% reduction in the objective function of the MF optimized design compared to the reference design is achieved. A pronounced difference in the penalty term between the MF optimized design and the adjusted design, MF.2, is apparent. This is attributed

Figure 13: Longitudinal slice through design MF.2 showing LES results of the internal mixture formation.

to the design MF.2 operating in a steady regime with the flow remaining attached to the flowbody while the MF optimized design produces more transient fluctuations due to the flow detachment. As scale-resolving simulations are required to identify such differences, this highlights the benefit of using MF optimization. However, LF RANS computations are still required for supplying general trends and for reducing the required number of computationally intensive HF simulations. Using the simplified wedge-shaped domain and RANS computations, only approx. 4.5 CPU-hours are required per LF simulation. In contrast, approx. 7600 CPU-hours are required for each three-dimensional HF LES. This illustrates that optimization purely based on the HF simulations would not be feasible.

The importance of the parameterization is evident, as design MF.2 cannot be generated using the chosen parameterization, yet exhibits the best performance in the HF simulation with respect to the selected objective metric, highlighting the need for a critical assessment of the optimized design. The benefit of MF optimization over SF optimization is further evaluated by comparing the MF optimum to an optimized design obtained solely from LF simulations.

4.2. Single-fidelity optimized design

For obtaining the SF optimized design, a regular Kriging surrogate model is constructed on the LF sampling points using the implementation in Dakota [60]. A genetic algorithm is applied and the resulting SF optimized design is presented in

Table 3: Values of the terms of the objective function for the reference designs, the SF optimum, the MF optimum and the manually adjusted optimum.

Objective Term	Simulation Type	Reference	Optimum SF	Optimum MF	Optimum adjusted
$\Phi_{\text{strat}} + 10 \Phi_{\text{hom}}$	RANS	10.14	1.94	–	–
$\Phi_{\text{strat}} + 10 \Phi_{\text{hom}}$	averaged LES	8.42	1.72	3.71	2.65
$2.5 \Phi_{\text{pen}}$	LES	2.48	3.57	0.45	0.01
Overall objective f	LES	10.90	5.29	4.16	2.66

Fig. 12 (ii). Contrary to the MF optimized design with a long flowbody, a shorter flowbody is favored in the RANS-only optimization. Still, the maximum radius of the flowbody is approximately the same for both designs. To investigate the transient behavior of the SF design, a LES of this design is carried out. The objective function values obtained from RANS computations and LESs of all presented designs, as well as the penalization term, Φ_{pen} , are listed in Tab. 3. It is apparent that the SF optimum yields a higher objective function value when evaluated in a LES both for the terms that are evaluated on the mean field, i.e. $\Phi_{\text{strat}} + 10 \Phi_{\text{hom}}$, as well as the transient penalization term. The larger penalty term indicates many richer-than-average hydrogen clusters close to the wall. Due to these clusters, it is hypothesized that the SF optimized design would produce a less stable flame with a higher propensity to flashback than the MF optimum.

4.3. Locally optimal designs

Since the non-reactive simulations may not capture all physical effects, extracting additional locally optimal designs for more detailed investigation can be beneficial. To this end, the local APPS algorithm is applied to the previously-constructed MF surrogate model. The algorithm is started from three distinct initial guesses to obtain different locally optimal designs. These initial guesses are determined by filtering the set of LF sampling points based on the objective function value to identify promising designs, while allowing a 30% increase over the LF optimum. The Euclidean distance of each point from the global optimum is calculated. Points that are sufficiently far away from the global optimum are selected as start-

ing points for the local optimization algorithm. After the APPS algorithm converged into an optimum, it is verified that this optimum is different from the global optimum. The obtained optima are then tested using HF simulations.

The local optimization algorithm returns three distinct local optima (c.f. Fig. 14) corresponding to each of the three identified promising starting points. The most notable difference is the long flowbody in the designs Opt.2 and Opt.3 compared to the global optimum. Opt.1 resembles the reference design but features a significantly larger hole size, hence reducing the velocity at which H_2 is ejected into the air-flow. For all optima, a flowbody with a large radius is favored. While Opt.3 resembles the adjusted design MF.2, it is noted that it features a concave surface while the adjusted design is convexly curved. The objective function values as well as the penalty term, Φ_{pen} , are summarized in Tab. 4. The concavely curved surface of Opt.3 favors flow detachment leading to increased transient fluctuations as reflected in the high penalty term compared to the MF optimized design with a convexly curved flowbody. All local optima are better than the SF optimized design due to decreased near-wall fluctuations resulting in a decreased penalty term, hence highlighting the impact of including LESs in the optimization.

4.4. Impact of averaging time frame on obtained optimum

The impact of the averaging period on the result of the optimization is analyzed next. To this end, the MF surrogate model is built on HF data that is averaged over a shorter time frame. The so-obtained optimal design is compared to the design that is av-

Table 4: Values of the terms of the objective function for the local optima.

Objective Term	Simulation Type	Opt. 1	Opt. 2	Opt. 3
$\Phi_{\text{strat}} + 10 \Phi_{\text{hom}}$	averaged LES	1.81	2.82	2.95
$2.5 \Phi_{\text{pen}}$	LES	2.41	1.69	2.09
Overall objective f	LES	4.22	4.51	5.04

Figure 14: Locally optimal designs obtained using the MF surrogate model and the APPS algorithm.

eraged over the full 0.1 s. In Fig. 15 the Euclidean distance from the optimum that is obtained utilizing the full averaging period, $\Delta \mathbf{x}^*$, is presented for different averaging time frames. With an increasing aver-

Figure 15: Distance of the obtained optimum from the MF optimum, $\Delta \mathbf{x}^*$, in relation to the averaging time frame.

aging time period, the obtained optimum converges toward the design that is obtained with the full averaging period. The distance of the optimum obtained using only half of the total averaging time from the fi-

nal optimum is only 0.3 mm. Therefore, the obtained optimum is not very sensitive to the averaging time frame and shorter simulation times seem sufficient to obtain an optimized design that complies with the manufacturing tolerances. Nevertheless, this may not generally hold for other design ideas with other parameterizations or objective functions.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we develop a multi-fidelity simulation-based shape optimization framework and apply it to the inverse design of a hydrogen burner nozzle with reduced flashback propensity and low NO_x emissions. The capabilities of the framework and the insights gained from its application can be summarized as follows:

- Despite the computational costs associated with HF simulations, they can be used effectively for shape optimization by utilizing simulation results of multiple fidelity levels.
- All steps to set up and run the simulations of the governing physical processes are fully automated, requiring no user interaction during optimization. These include modification of the geometry, mesh generation, setup of boundary conditions, and execution of the solver.
- During optimization, linear, and bound constraints to the design variables can be taken into account.
- All nozzle designs obtained with this MF optimization framework surpass the SF optimum in the chosen objective metric. They succeed in producing the desired mixture characteristics at the burner nozzle outlet.

The objective metric was constructed under certain assumptions regarding the influence of mixture characteristics on the flame behavior. These assumptions

require experimental validation, particularly with respect to NO_x emissions and flame stability. The primary goal of the present optimization framework is to accelerate the overall design process by providing an improved initial design, thereby reducing the number of iterations between manufacturing, experimental characterization, and subsequent design refinement. Recent findings indicate that the optimized designs may lead to lower pollutant emissions and a reduced propensity to flame flashback [32].

Due to the modularity of the framework, it may be applied to other inverse design problems in the future. To this end, the following requirements must be satisfied: For MF optimization, simulations of varying fidelity levels must be available that describe the dominating physical effects with sufficient accuracy to predict trends. Further, the cost of each HF evaluation must be low enough to allow $\sim 10^1$ simulations.

Some aspects of the design optimization of combustion devices that leverage the capabilities of AM warrant further investigation in the future. The effect of rough surfaces due to additive manufacturing on the mixture formation was neglected in the present simulations and must be further investigated. As indicated in different studies [68, 69], this surface roughness may have an effect on the flame's emissions and its stability through modifications of local recirculation zones. However, a targeted introduction of rough surfaces through additive manufacturing may be utilized for locally enhancing mixing processes.

Since the optimized designs ultimately depend on the parameterized initial design, future studies could explore different design ideas and parameterizations. In particular, the introduction of swirl-inducing nozzle components may be beneficial for increasing the homogeneity of the hydrogen-air mixture in the angular direction.

Leveraging the capabilities of the chosen MF surrogate model, the optimization framework may be extended to an arbitrary number of fidelity levels. Furthermore, the efficiency of the optimization framework may be further improved in future work by implementing a Bayesian optimization approach that adaptively places sampling points based on the uncertainty of the approximation, which can be estimated using the (hierarchical) Kriging model [23, 70, 71].

Additionally, if the sensitivities of the objective function on the design variables are available, e.g. through adjoint optimization approaches, surrogate models that include this gradient information may require less sampling points for building an accurate approximation.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Raphael Strickling: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft; **Faizan Habib Vance:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **Arne Scholtissek:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

Data availability statement

The code developed in this study can be accessed at [10.5281/zenodo.19327991](https://zenodo.org/record/19327991)[72].

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